

D7.2 Initial Data Management Plan

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Executive summary

This deliverable DMP describes the methodology for data management that is planned to be employed in the framework of the GUESTXR project. The described methodology aims to safeguard the sound management of the data collected and generated during the course of the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them FAIR. Moreover, the DMP identifies the anticipated activities required for making data FAIR, outlines the provisions pertaining to their security as well as addresses the ethical aspects revolving around their collection/generation.

The DMP is considered to be a living document in the framework of GUESTXR and will be updated as needed throughout the course of the project taking into account its latest developments and available results. In fact, the DMP will be reviewed and revalidated before each periodic project management report, and any updates will be included in the periodic project management reports. Ad hoc updates, may also be realised when deemed necessary, with a view to delivering an accurate, up-to-date and comprehensive DMP before the completion of the project (D7.5 Final Data Management Plan). These updates will also be appended on the periodic project management reports. This deliverable is delivered at M6 of the project and is updated based on the latest information available up to the month of delivery.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DL	Deep Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
ML	Machine Learning
XR	Extended Reality

Introduction

The current document constitutes the Data Management Plan (DMP) elaborated in the framework of GUESTXR, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme.

GUESTXR's main objective is to develop GUESTXR, a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses eXtended Reality (virtual and augmented reality) as the medium to bring people together for immersive, synchronous face-to-face interaction with positive social outcomes. The critical innovation is the intervention of artificial agents that learn over time to help the virtual social gathering realise its aims. This is an agent that we refer to as "The Guest" that exploits Machine Learning to learn how to facilitate the meeting towards specific outcomes. Underpinning this is neuroscience and social psychology research on group behaviour, which will deliver rules to Agent Based Models (ABM). The combination of AI with immersive systems (including haptics and immersive audio), virtual and augmented reality will be a hugely challenging research task, given the vagaries of social meetings and individual behaviour.

GUESTXR technology will be demonstrated in at least three different use cases: conflict resolution, people with communication difficulties (i.e., hearing impairments) and discussion on controversial topics such as climate change. An Open Call will be held to bring in artistic support and additional use cases from wider society.

Significant work is dedicated to ethics "by design", to identify problems and look eventually towards an appropriate regulatory framework for such socially interactive systems.

To this end, GUESTXR brings together a well-balanced and complementary consortium, that consists of 8 partners across 6 different countries, as presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1: GUESTXR Partners List

No	Partner Legal Name	Short Name	Country
1	FUNDACIO EURECAT	EUT	Spain
2	VIRTUAL BODYWORKS SL	EUT	Spain
3	REICHMAN UNIVERSITY	IDCH	Israel
4	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	UM	Netherlands
5	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE	INRIA	France
6	UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI	UW	Poland
7	G.TEC MEDICAL ENGINEERING GMBH	G.TEC	Austria
8	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	UB	Spain

In this context, all partners of GUESTXR's consortium adhere to sound data management in order to ensure that the meaningful data collected, processed and/or generated throughout the duration of the project is well-managed, archived and preserved, in line with the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 and according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Along these lines, this initial version of GUESTXR's DMP aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Describe the data management lifecycle for the data to be collected and/or generated in the framework of GUESTXR, serving as a key element of good data management.
- Outline the methodology employed to safeguard the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated as well as to make it Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).
- Provide information on the data that will be collected and/or generated and the way in which it will be handled during and after the end of the project along with the standards applied to this end.
- Describe what kind of data and the way for making them accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders as well as its curation and preservation.
- Present an estimation of the resources allocated to make data FAIR, while also identifying the responsibilities pertaining to data management and addressing data security.

In order to achieve its objectives, the DMP takes into account and builds upon common best practices and guidelines for sharing the project's data (such as the practices described by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives tour guide on data management, UK Data Service, etc.) and facilitating open access (through the use of openly accessible repositories) to the data collected/generated while taking into account the recommendations provided by the European Commission.

With the above in mind, this version of the DMP is structured in the following topics:

- Introductory information about the DMP, the context in which it has been elaborated as well as about its objectives and structure.
- Summary of the data to be collected or/and generated during the activities of GUESTXR including the purpose of its collection/generation as well as its types and formats. Additionally, it outlines its origin, expected volume and the stakeholders that may find it useful.
- Methodology that is applied in the framework of GUESTXR in order to safeguard the effective management of data across their entire lifecycle, making it FAIR.
- Estimation of the resources required for making the project's data FAIR, while also identifying data management responsibilities.
- Data security strategy applied within the context of GUESTXR along with the respective secure storage solutions employed.
- Ethical aspects as well as other relevant considerations pertaining to the data collected/generated during the implementation of the project, including management of personal data.
- Next steps foreseen in the framework of the project with respect to its data management plan.

Finally, there is an Annexes section that includes: a privacy policy that should be used as the base for the project's Web Portal privacy policy, as well as the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet used in the implementation of the project's activities that collect/generate data. This section also includes a questionnaire about the Data Protection Officer from each organisation regarding the management of personal data.

The DMP is not a fixed document. It evolves during the lifespan of the project. Ad hoc updates will be realised (if necessary), to include new data, better detail and/or reflect changes in the methodology or other aspects relevant to its management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. These updates will be documented in the Periodic Reports.

1 Data summary

GUESTXR plans to collect and generate meaningful non-sensitive and sensitive data that may fall into the special categories¹ of personal data as those are described within the General Data Protection Regulation² (GDPR). This data may be quantitative, qualitative or a blend of those in nature and will be analysed from a range of methodological perspectives with a view to producing insights that will successfully feed GUESTXR's activities, enable the members to deliver evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project. With that in mind, the second chapter of the Data Management Plan (DMP) starts by explaining the purpose for which this data will be collected/ generated and how it relates with GUESTXR. It proceeds by describing the different types and formats of this data as well as its origin and expected volume, before concluding with an overview of potential stakeholders for whom it may prove useful for re-use.

1.1 Purpose of data collection/generation and its relation to the project

In order to successfully meet its objectives and ensure the production of evidence-based results, GUESTXR entails several activities during which data will be collected/ generated. The purpose for which this data is collected/ generated is interrelated with the objective of the activity during which it is produced.

In particular, these activities along with their objectives in the framework of GUESTXR are as follows:

- **Design & development phase:** Design and development of ML agent and the meeting shared space to be implemented in the GUESTXR's pilots (use cases). This includes the data related to the ABM that will feed the ML agent derived from social psychology and neuroscience of emotions. This point also includes the data related to

¹ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

ethics that will be the base for the development of the technology according to “Ethics-by-design methodology”.

- **Use cases implementation:** Monitoring, evaluation and validation of GUESTXR’s developments and pilots, in order to improve and fine-tune their design based on data and feedback collected/generated by developers, users and every engaged stakeholder participating in the project’s pilot activities or in various use case workshops for testing.
- **Dissemination and communication:** Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results of the project with a view to measuring the impact of the project’s relevant activities, accordingly fine-tuning GUESTXR’s strategy in this respect as well as fulfilling its reporting requirements towards the Commission.

Along these lines, consortium partners acknowledge the importance of this data, and thus they will handle it according to the national and/or European laws especially with respect to the processing of personal data.

The following section provides further details on the different types and formats of data collected/generated during the project’s activities.

1.2 Types and formats of collected/generated data

During the activities of GUESTXR, data of different nature will be collected/ generated. The types of this data can be described in many different ways depending on the source and physical format of the data. Nevertheless, data is often seen as how it is created/ captured³. Examples include electronic text documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires and transcripts, among others. Another way to think about data is the format in which different data types (qualitative, quantitative, etc.) are stored. Along these lines, GUESTXR’s data will, when possible, be available in easily accessible formats, such as post scripts (e.g. pdf, xps, etc.), machine readable formats (xml, html, etc.), spreadsheets (e.g. xlsx, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g. docx, rtf, etc.), compressed formats (e.g. rar, zip, etc.) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the frame of which it is produced.

In this respect, special attention will be paid in using open formats (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and/or machine-readable formats (such as xml, json, rdf, html, etc.) when possible in order to enhance the interoperability and re-use of GUESTXR’s data. In doing so, we will be providing data that is easily readable and freely usable in any software program employed by third parties interested in utilizing the data.

With that in mind, the type and formats of the data collected/generated in the framework of GUESTXR can be divided into 3 main categories, namely (i) data collected/generated by direct input methods, (ii) from users of the GUESTXR Developments (iii) data collected/generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities, as further described in the following subsections.

³Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>

1.2.1 Data collected/generated through direct input methods

In the framework of GUESTXR, direct input methods encompass methodologies for collecting data through interactions between consortium partners and external stakeholders (or other consortium partners), with the latter providing data to the former. Along these lines, external stakeholders may assume the role of a data subject that is a natural person whose personal data is being processed. In particular, the identification and selection of suitable data subjects are based on purposeful sampling according to which data are provided to be used in the context of GUESTXR developments.

In this context, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected/generated during the course of GUESTXR:

- Quantitative data is numerical and acquired through counting or measuring. Examples of quantitative data are the duration of a participant's intervention, the number of interventions, etc. This data may be represented by ordinal, interval or ratio scales and lend themselves to statistical manipulation.
- Qualitative data, sometimes referred to as categorical data, is data that can be arranged into categories based on physical traits, colours or anything that does not have a number associated with it. Moreover, written documents, interviews, and various forms of in-field observation are all sources of qualitative data. Examples of qualitative data are the types of body expressions, country of origin, etc.

With that in mind, further details with respect to the different types and formats of data that will be collected through direct input methods under the frame of GUESTXR are provided in the remainder of this subsection.

User needs and requirements regarding the shared meeting space

This data will be collected by the UB during the qualitative survey that will be conducted in the framework of GUESTXR, which will aim at revealing the needs and requirements of prospective users and stakeholders of the GUESTXR sharing meeting space. For this purpose data in the form of interview transcripts or use case specification may be collected by means of email semi-structured interviews.

Ethics

This data will be collected by UM during the qualitative survey that will be conducted in the framework of GUESTXR, which will give information on the ethical aspects to be considered in the development of the technology.

Feedback on the Use Cases

This data will be collected through a survey/short interview of pilot participants as well as members of the project's User Group identified as potential early adopters / lead users, with a view to gaining meaningful feedback on how the business models and or the exploitable results of the GUESTXR Project may be refined and further shaped to fit the needs of potential users and stakeholders. The data will be of both qualitative as well as quantitative nature addressing the appropriateness and acceptance of different elements of the different Pilot cases.

Data collected/generated through direct input methods will be stored in standard .docx as well as .xlsx formats. These kinds of formats allow the documentation of information coming from various files and documents so that it exists in a single location. By doing

so, it is possible to circulate raw data from transcripts, as well as text, images and other objects from other files to one document file or multiple tabs of a single spreadsheet. Moreover, both formats can be immediately converted into open and machine-readable formats (such as .xml and .csv) boosting the interoperability and re-usability of the datasets produced during the implementation of GUESTXR.

1.2.2 Data collected/generated during the development and testing of the technology (implementation of the Use Cases)

GUESTXR will develop a ML agent that will interact with the participants of the meeting that will take place in a shared VR space. Furthermore, GuestXR will implement at least four Use Cases addressed to different groups of people that will test and use the technology. In particular GUESTXR will develop the following use cases:

- Conflict resolution
- Hearing impairment
- Climate Change
- Indeterminate Use Case selected after the Open Call.

These use cases will be used as a pilot in order to evaluate research advances and their applicability in relevant context.

Table 2: Expected Data Types from related GUESTXR Use Cases shows the type of data expected to be processed in relation to the implementation of the use cases.

Table 2: Expected Data Types from related GUESTXR Use Cases

Type Of Data	WP	Partner
Audiometry	WP4	EUT
Personal Data including health data	WP4	EUT
Usage statistics	WP6	EUT
Usage statistics	WP6	EUT
Personal data	WP6	EUT
Activity statistics	WP6	EUT
Personal data	WP6	EUT
Activity statistics	WP6	EUT
Body movement trajectory analysis, voice analysis, questionnaire analysis	WP3	VBW
User behavior in multi-user VR	WP1	IDCH
User behavior in multi-user VR	WP1	IDCH
User behavior in multi-user VR	WP1	IDCH
Brain imaging data	WP4	IDCH

Type Of Data	WP	Partner
Participant brain imaging data and reaction time data	WP2	UM
Participant behavioral data	WP2	UM
User generated	WP5	UM
Behavioral & physiological data + User generated	WP4	INRIA
Behavioral & physiological data + User generated	WP4	INRIA
Machine & user generated	WP2	GTEC
Opinion data body movements and amount of talking	WP2	UB
Opinion data body movements and amount of talking	WP2	UB

1.2.3 Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities

1.2.3.1 Social media statistics (including Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)

This data will be collected/ generated through a periodic monitoring of the project’s social media statistics (including Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project’s social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication. With that in mind, the data will be both qualitative as well as quantitative in nature addressing the metrics reached on each channel (e.g. followers, tweets impressions on twitter, friends, likes on LinkedIn etc.). Additionally, this data will be followed by an analysis of the results stemming from it and possible ways to improve the results so as to reach the project’s targets. All in all, the data will be stored in a Microsoft excel file (.xlsx) while at the same time the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard word document (.docx).

1.2.3.2 Data collected from project events (e.g. workshops, webinars, stakeholder engagement events, etc.)

This data will be collected in 2 ways during the implementation of the project, that is:

- The stakeholder engagement events organised by GUESTXR (such as the User Group event, conference workshop, closure event, etc.) consisting of the participants lists that will enclose contact information about the participants;
- The participation of GUESTXR consortium partners in third party relevant events to reach out and engage stakeholders, thus includes general information about the events attended and their outreach.

Along these lines, this data is collected so as to keep track of the results of stakeholder engagement activities and provide the opportunity to project partners to report on these activities. Moreover, this data will be updated every time a partner attends an event, or a partner organises an event. Finally, the data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx).

1.2.3.3 Newsletter subscriptions (e.g. contact details of subscribers)

A subscription form hosted in the project's web portal will aid the collection of this data in which any interested stakeholder can freely provide their contact details in a dedicated sign-up form so as to receive the most up-to-date news and outcomes of the project. A newsletter will be sent to subscribers once per 6 months. With that in mind, this data will be collected so that interested stakeholders can be informed about the GUESTXR project as well as the Use Cases. Along these lines, the data will be comprised of a list of stakeholders along with their personal information. In this context, the data collected include the following information: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name. A copy of this contact list will be stored to the Newsletter email server which will be used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list will be used and protected according to email server's Privacy Policy.

1.2.3.4 Data from dissemination and communication

This data will be collected through a periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, posts in the blogs, etc. The data will consist of a list of publications and posts published by the consortium partners. The purpose of collecting this data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project. For this purpose, a template has been shared with all partners to recommend activities to be performed and log the activities they performed. The template is provided also online so as the partners can directly update their input. Finally, all the data will be integrated in a single excel file (.xlsx).

1.3 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

In the context of GUESTXR, new data will be collected/ generated by consortium partners as well as external stakeholders participating in the activities of the project and/or during the use cases execution. With that in mind and aside consortium partners, external groups of stakeholders from which new data will originate include:

- Knowledge, technology and innovation solution providers (e.g. within academic institutions and their technology/knowledge transfer offices, non-university public research organisations, research and technology organisations, high-tech SMEs and large enterprises, etc.).
- Policy designers and implementers at regional, national and EU level (e.g. in regional/national/EU authorities, development agencies, etc.).

Moreover, specific pre-existing data may be utilised within the context of the project as well.

1.4 Expected size of data

GUESTXR entails a series of activities aiming at setting the stage for and ultimately facilitating the demand-driven evidence-based development, testing, evaluation, validation and fine-tuning of its developments and value propositions. With that in mind, Table 3: Expected Size of Data

3 presents the different activities planned to be implemented during the course of the project in which data is collected/ generated, the types and formats of the data as well as the expected size of the data.

Table 3: Expected Size of Data

No	Name Of Activity	Data	Type Of data	Format Of Data	Expected Size Of Data
EUR_1	Subjective testing of the ML algorithm for sound enhancement for hearing aids users	Audiometry of the user, Age group, Type of Hearing Loss and preferences in the option matrix	Audiometry Personal Data including health data	xml file	50
EUR_2	Subjective testing of the ML algorithm for sound enhancement for normal listening users	Audiometry of the user, Age group and preferences in the option matrix	Audiometry Personal Data including health data	xml file	50
EUR_3	Periodic monitoring of the project's social media statistics	Social media statistics	Usage statistics	xml file	500 k
EUR_4	Periodic monitoring of the project's website statistics	Statistical information on the browsing of users is collected through third-party cookies and analysed using MATOMO	Usage statistics	xml file	5 MB
EUR_5	Newsletter subscription	Contact details from stakeholder interested in the project Including: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name.	Personal data	Cvs file	depending on the size of the community of interest
EUR_6	Data from dissemination and communication activities	List of dissemination and communication activities done by partners.	Activity statistics	xml file	50
EUR_7	Data from media outlets / journalists	A file with personal data for journalists and media outlets of interest will be created by	Personal data	Xml file	50

No	Name Of Activity	Data	Type Of data	Format Of Data	Expected Size Of Data
		EUT by filtering their media database			
EUR_8	Data collected for project events	List of stakeholder engagement events organised by GuestXR	Activity statistics	xml file	500 k
VBW_1	Meetings in persistent shared environment if data collection was agreed on.	tracked body movements (Head and hands, maybe eyes), voice, questionnaire responses	body movement trajectory analysis, voice analysis, questionnaire analysis	json and audio files, if required encrypted by advanced encryption	few gigabytes
IDCH_1	Y1-Y2	multi-user VR	user behavior in multi-user VR	misc log files	~50 participants
IDCH_2	Y2-Y3	multi-user VR + RL	user behavior in multi-user VR	misc log files	misc log files
IDCH_3	Y3-Y4	multi-user XR + RL	user behavior in multi-user VR	misc log files	misc log files
IDCH_4	fMRI experiment	fMRI data for multisensory integration	fMRI data for multisensory integration	csv files, DICOM files	100GB
UM_1	fMRI experiment to investigate representation of expressive body language	fMRI data, behavioural reaction time data	Participant brain imaging data and reaction time data	csv files, DICOM files	100GB
UM_2	Behavioural experiment to test body language recognition	Behavioural accuracy and reaction time data	Participant behavioural data	xlsx file, csv files	100MB
UM_3 (Ethics)	Stakeholder interviews/co-creation workshops	transcripts and recordings of expert interviews, noted from co-creation workshops or	user generated		not to exceed 100GB

No	Name Of Activity	Data	Type Of data	Format Of Data	Expected Size Of Data
		other sessions			
INRIA_1	WP4 User experiments - Multisensory displays	VR user interactions	Behavioral & physiological data + User generated	csv & xml files	A few Gbytes
INRIA_2	WP5 Use cases and integration process	VR interactions	Behavioral & physiological data + User generated	csv & xml files	A few Gbytes
GTEC_1	Development of electrophysiology training environment	biosignals, e.g. EEG	Machine & user generated	mat file	10
UB1	Studying the responses of people in shared VR	Unknown at this time.	Opinion data body movements and amount of talking	Spreadsheet.	Unknown
UB2	Studying various mechanisms for conflict resolution in VR.	Unknown at this time.	Opinion data body movements and amount of talking	Spreadsheet.	Unknown

* The estimated expected size of the data is based on the adjusted size of data generated via similar activities of project partners in the past unless otherwise indicated.

1.5 Data utility

The stakeholders that may find meaningful utility for the data to be collected/generated by the project (both within as well as outside of GUESTXR's consortium) along with the benefits that could arise for them by utilizing this data, are concisely presented in the table that follows.

Table 4: Data Utility

Stakeholder Group	Data Utility
Researchers in the field of Extended Reality and machine Learning	The field of Extended Reality, albeit having promising potential for generating new technologies and opportunities with great market and social value, appears to have a large potential of further research worldwide. Under this light, GUESTXR's data can provide researchers

	in the multi-disciplinary and cross-cutting field of XR with valuable insights into how ML is implemented in XR and approached in GUESTXR with data generated from practical applications in the GUESTXR pilots and the GUESTXR developments. Interested researchers may re-use the data of GUESTXR as a basis to replicate similar studies within the same or different contexts as well as to design and launch new studies, generating comparable research findings to further advance the field and shed ample light on the workings of ML in XR.
Policy makers, Standardization bodies and agencies, implementers and funders	Throughout its duration, GUESTXR is set on collecting and producing data on the safe application of ML in Virtual Reality environment. Data generated to this end, may find great utility in the hands of experts who design, implement and/or fund relevant innovation and business support policies. Indeed, collected data on the application of XR in pilot cases, as well as identified best practices, can provide experts with reliable input to analyse the potential opportunities, successes (and failures) generated under the project.
Project partners	The data collected/generated during GUESTXR is of paramount utility for project partners in order to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project. Indeed, this data will enable the co-design, development, validation and fine-tuning of the project's pilots. Moreover, the data will be used to design, improve and validate the piloted solutions. At the same time, this data may hold meaningful utility for project partners beyond the end of the project as well, enabling them to build and capitalise upon interesting ideas and opportunities that may emerge to ensure the exploitation and maximization of the results produced by GUESTXR.

2 Fair Data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanisms

The GUESTXR DMP aims to safeguard the sound management of the data collected and generated during the course of the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them FAIR. GUESTXR places special emphasis in enhancing the discoverability of the data collected/generated during the course of its activities. To this end, the project follows a metadata-driven approach so as to increase the searchability of the data, while also facilitating its understanding and reuse. Metadata is defined as "data about data" or "information about information". It is usually structured textual information that describes something about the creation, content, or context of a digital resource – be it a single file, part of a single file, or a collection of many files. Metadata is the glue which links information and data across the World Wide Web. It is the tool that helps people to discover, manage, describe, preserve and build relationships with and between digital resources.

In particular, three distinct types of metadata have been identified and are presented below:

- Descriptive metadata, used to identify and describe collections and related information re-sources. Descriptive metadata at the local level helps with searching and retrieving. In an online environment, descriptive metadata helps to

discover resources. Most of the times include information such as the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.

- Administrative metadata is used to facilitate the management of information resources. It is helpful for both short-term and long-term management and processing of data. This is information that will not usually be relevant to the public but will be essential for staff to manage collections internally. Such metadata may be location information, acquisition information, etc.
- Structural metadata enables navigation and presentation of electronic resources. It documents how the components of an item are organized. Examples of structural metadata could be the way in which pages are ordered to form chapters of a book, a photograph that is included in a manuscript or a scrapbook or the JPEG and TIF files that were created from the original photograph negative, linked together.

With that in mind, data produced/used during GUESTXR is discoverable with metadata suitable to its content and format. To this end, the project employs metadata standards to produce rich and consistent metadata to support the long-term discovery; use and integrity of its data (see Subsection 2.1.5 for more details on the metadata standards adopted by GUESTXR).

In parallel, to further increase data discoverability, the data produced by GUESTXR and deemed open for sharing and reuse, will be deposited to suitable infrastructure that serve the aforementioned purposes. Such an infrastructure can be an open data repository. The current planning involves depositing data to Zenodo⁴, an open data repository. This data repository, created by OpenAIRE⁵ and CERN⁶, has been chosen to enable open access to the project's open data free of charge. In fact, Zenodo builds and operates a simple service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions, among others, to share and showcase research results (including data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It accepts any file format, promotes peer-reviewed openly accessible research, allows the creation of own collections and it is available free of charge both for GUESTXR to upload and share data as well as for other stakeholders to explore, download and reuse this data.

Moreover, by employing this data repository, the data produced during the implementation of the project can be located by means of a standard identification mechanism. Indeed, GUESTXR will be able to assign globally resolvable Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) on any data uploaded to Zenodo. An identifier is a unique identification code that is applied to a dataset, so that it can be unambiguously referenced. For example, a catalogue number is an identifier for a particular specimen and an ISBN code is an identifier for a particular book. PIDs are simply maintainable identifiers that allow for permanent reference to a digital object. In other words, PIDs are a way of giving digital resources, such as documents, images and data records, a unique and persistent reference number.

⁴ www.zenodo.org

⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁶ <https://home.cern/>

In addition, as a digital repository, Zenodo registers Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for all submitted data through DataCite⁷, which is the leading global non-profit organisation that provides PIDs (and specifically DOIs) for research data, and preserves these submissions using the safe and trusted foundation of CERN's data centre, alongside the biggest scientific dataset in the world, the LHC's 100PB Big Data store. This means that the data preserved in Zenodo will be accessible for years to come, and the DOIs will function as perpetual links to the resources. DOIs remain valuable since they are future proofed against Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or even protocol changes, through resolvers (such as DOI⁸). With that in mind, an example of a DOI retrieved from this open repository follows the structure illustrated by Figure 1: Example of a typical DOI created by Zenodo

Figure 1: Example of a typical DOI created by Zenodo

At the same time, datasets not uploaded to Zenodo will be deposited in a searchable resource (i.e. the web portal of the project) and utilise well-tailored identification mechanisms as well, in the form of standard naming conventions that will safeguard their consistency and make them easily locatable for project partners within the framework of the project. The following subsection provides further details in this respect.

2.1.2 Naming Conventions

Following a consistent set of naming conventions in the development of the project's data files can greatly enhance their searchability. With that in mind, GUESTXR creates consistent data file names that provide clues to their content, status and versioning, while also increasing their discoverability. In doing so, project partners as well as interested stakeholders can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort them.

According to the UK Data Archive⁹ a best practice in naming convention is to create brief yet meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming convention should avoid the utilisation of spaces, dots and special characters (such as & or !), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file.

With that in mind and to facilitate the reference of the datasets that will be produced during its implementation, GUESTXR will employ a standard naming convention that integrates versioning and will take into account the possibility of creating multiple datasets during an activity that entails data collection/generation. Indeed, GUESTXR's naming convention considers this issue and addresses it by employing a unique element that captures the number of datasets that are produced under the same activity.

In particular, the naming convention employed by the project is described below.

⁷ <https://www.datacite.org/>

⁸ <http://dx.doi.org/>

⁹ <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/format/organising>

GUESTXR _ [Name of Study] _ [Number of dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- **GUESTXR:** The name of the project.
- **Name of Study:** A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- **Number of dataset:** An indication of the number assigned to the dataset.
- **Issue Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).
- **Version number:** The versioning number of a dataset.

With the above in mind, some indicative examples to showcase the naming structure applied in the context of GUESTXR are provided below. These examples aim only to showcase the naming conventions and do not necessarily correspond to actual datasets.

- GUESTXR_NeedsAndRequirements_Dataset1_2022.02.20_v1 – The first dataset generated within the framework of the survey conducted to identify the needs and requirements of the diverse project stakeholders. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 20th of February 2022 (20/02/2022).
- GUESTXR_HRCValidation_Dataset2_2022.03.15_v2 – The second dataset created in the process of validating and improving the VR platform. The last modification of this dataset, which in this case produced the second version of the dataset, was on the 15th of March 2022 (15/03/2022).

2.1.3 Search Keyword

The project's data will be provided with search keywords with a view to optimizing its use by interested stakeholders during its entire lifetime. With that in mind, the metadata standards employed by GUESTXR provide opportunities for tagging the data collected/generated and its content with keywords. In general, keywords are a subset of metadata and include words and phrases used to name data. In the context of GUESTXR, keywords are used to add valuable information to the data collected/generated as well as to facilitate the description and interpretation of its content and value.

Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The “who”, the “what”, the “when”, the “where”, and the “why” should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.
- Relevant, understandable and clear keywording ought to be sought.

In general, the keywords will comprise terms related to Extended Reality, Virtual Reality as well as Augmented Reality. The keywords will accurately reflect the content of the datasets and avoid words used only once or twice within them.

2.1.4 Versioning

Versioning of information makes a revision of datasets uniquely identifiable and can be used to determine whether and how data changed over time and to define specifically which version the creators/editors are working with. Moreover, effective data versioning enables understanding if a newer version of a dataset is available and which are the changes between the different versions allowing for comparisons and preventing confusion. In this context, **a clear version number indicator is used in the naming convention** of every data file produced during the course of the GUESTXR in order to facilitate the identification of different versions.

2.1.5 Standards for metadata creation

GUESTXR employs standards for creating metadata for the data collected/generated by the project, with a view to describing it with rich metadata and thus improving their discoverability and searchability. As a result, effective searching, improved digital curation and easy sharing will be realized. In addition, the metadata standards applied enable the integration of metadata from a variety of sources into other technical systems.

With that in mind, for GUESTXR's openly available data such as the metadata standards provided by Zenodo will be used. In particular Zenodo creates metadata to accompany the datasets that are uploaded to its repository, extending their reach to a wider audience of interested stakeholders. This metadata can be exported in several standard formats, including open and machine-readable ones (such as MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema), following the guidelines of OpenAIRE and are stored by Zenodo in JSON-format according to a defined JSON¹⁰ schema.

Project data not available for re-use, will also be annotated with open and machine-readable metadata following the Dublin Core Metadata standard. The Dublin Core Metadata element set (covered by the international standard ISO 15836) is a standard which can be easily understood and implemented and as such, is one of the best known metadata standards. It was originally developed as a core set of elements for describing the content of web pages and enabling their search and retrieval. Among the reasons for selecting this standard is also the fact that Zenodo is compatible with Dublin Core metadata formats and thus any initially closed data, that may become open at a later stage (e.g. due to a change in the consortium's policy), will not lose its metadata. With that said, the Dublin Core metadata standard is a simple yet effective set for creating rich metadata that will describe a wide range of resources. The fifteen element "Dublin Core" described in this standard is part of a larger set of metadata vocabularies and technical specifications maintained by the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI¹¹). The full set of vocabularies, also includes sets of resource classes, vocabulary encoding schemes, and syntax encoding schemes. The Dublin Core Generator¹², online metadata generator can be used to produce the different metadata elements required.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 Openly available and closed data

GUESTXR Project is part of the H2020 and aims to "make the data collected/generated openly available with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access". Under this light, the project adopts the good practice encouraged by the ORDP, namely that of making data as open as possible and as closed as necessary. This calls for project partners to disseminate the project's data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed in the collection/generation of this data, with a view to maximising the beneficial impact of GUESTXR.

Only anonymised and aggregated data will be made open to ensure that data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from the

¹⁰ For more information on the JSON format and the JSON schema visit the following website: <http://json-schema.org/>

¹¹ <http://dublincore.org/>

¹² dublincoregenerator.com)

project. The project partner serving as the data controller in each case will undertake all the necessary anonymization procedures to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable. More details on data management responsibilities are provided in Section 3.2.

To this end, it is important to keep in mind that during the process of data anonymization, data identifiers need to be removed, generalised, aggregated or distorted. Moreover, anonymization is different than pseudonymization, which falls under a distinct category in the GDPR - anonymization theoretically destroys any way of identifying the data subject, while pseudonymization allows for the data subject to be re-identified with additional information. Along these lines, the table below provides a list of good practices for the anonymisation of quantitative and qualitative data derived from the tour guide on data management of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)¹³.

Table 5: Data anonymization best practices

Type Of Data	Good Practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Removing or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable.</i> • <i>Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. As a general rule, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality.</i> • <i>Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclose free-text responses with more general text.</i> <p><i>Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.</i></p>
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information;</i> • <i>Plan anonymization at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing).</i> • <i>Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research;</i> • <i>Use 'search and replace' techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelt words are not missed;</i>

¹³ Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>

Type Of Data	Good Practices
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify replacements in text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg>word to be anonymised</seg>; <p>Create an anonymization log (also known as a de-anonymization key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.</p>

With that in mind, the following table presents the data collected/generated during the course of the project that will be made openly available. In case certain data cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), a justification for that choice should be provided.

Table 6: Data Availability

Partner	Data	Availability out of the consortium	Notes
EUT	Subjective testing of the ML algorithm for sound enhancement for hearing aids users	Closed	-
EUT	Subjective testing of the ML algorithm for sound enhancement for normal listening users	Closed	-
EUT	Social media statistics	Closed	-
EUT	Website statistics	Closed	-
EUT	Newsletter subscription	Closed	-
EUT	Data from dissemination and communication activities	Open	-
EUT	Data from media outlets / journalists	Closed	-
EUT	Data collected for project events	Closed	-
VBW	Meetings in persistent shared environment if data collection was agreed on.	Open, if agreed	TBC
IDCH	User behavior in multi-user VR	Could be Open	TBC
IDCH	User behavior in multi-user VR	Could be Open	TBC
IDCH	User behavior in multi-user VR	Could be Open	TBC
IDCH	fMRI experiments	Closed	-
UM	fMRI experiment to investigate representation of expressive body language	Closed	-

Partner	Data	Availability out of the consortium	Notes
UM	Behavioural experiment to test body language recognition	Closed	-
UM	Stakeholder interviews/co-creation workshops	Open	-
INRIA	WP4 User experiments - Multisensory displays	Closed	-
INRIA	WP5 Use cases and integration process	Could be open (integration process)	TBC
GTEC	Development of electrophysiology training environment	Open	-
UB	Studying the responses of people in shared VR	Could be Open	TBC
UB	Studying various mechanisms for conflict resolution in VR.	Could be Open	TBC

It is important to note that all personal data collected / generated will be considered as closed data prior to their anonymization and aggregation to safeguard the confidentiality of the data subjects.

This data will be securely stored by the consortium partners that collected them to be preserved in their respective records only for as long as necessary for them to comply with their contractual obligations and no longer than 5 years from the project's completion. During this period the personal data will be accessible only by authorised individuals of GUESTXR's consortium partner that collected this data and of the REA. After this period the personal data will be deleted from the respective consortium partner's records.

2.2.2 Data accessibility and availability

Public access to the open data will be made available through Zenodo, which will automatically link to OpenAIRE. The data will be fully accessible thanks to the included metadata and the search facility available on Zenodo. At the same time, closed data will be stored and shared amongst authorised members of the consortium through web portal of the project.

2.2.3 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

GUESTXR emphasises the accessibility of the data collected/generated during the course of the project. With that in mind, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation should be needed, in order to access the data. Stakeholders can access the data by simply using their web browser (e.g. Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, etc.) through their computers (either desktop or laptop), smart phones and/or tablets. More specifically, they first need to access Zenodo through its webpage (following the link <https://zenodo.org/>) and utilise the search engine of the repository to search for interesting data. By typing the name of the project (or any other relevant

keyword connected to the data) the search engine will direct the use to the project's data, ready to be explored and re-used. Moreover, since the data will be available in open formats we will be ensuring that they can correctly be read by a range of different software programs that most of the people employ in their everyday lives.

Closed data can be accessed only by authorised project partners through the shared site [GuestXR - Home \(sharepoint.com\)](https://sharepoint.com). Again, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation are needed to this end. Nevertheless, this SharePoint site is accessible only with the provision of their unique username and password combination. Therefore, they first need to login the GUESTXR SharePoint through their digital device (e.g. computers, smartphones, tables, etc.) and provide their respective usernames and passwords. Then, they can find the uploaded data categorised under the file browser section.

2.2.4 Data, metadata, code and documentation repositories

GUESTXR's open data along with their linking metadata as well as any relevant code and documentation (if applicable) required to access this data, will be deposited to and securely stored by Zenodo. It is quite unlikely that Zenodo will have to terminate its operation and stop providing its services, but in such a case all data, metadata, code and documentation uploaded by GUESTXR will be transferred and hosted to other suitable repositories¹⁴ without undue delay. In this respect, it is important to note that, since all of GUESTXR's openly available data will make use of PIDs (i.e. DOIs), the links to the data will not be affected. In parallel, GUESTXR's data that will not be openly available for sharing will be deposited, together with their accompanying metadata, code and documentation (if necessary), to the project SharePoint site.

2.2.5 Restrictions

By utilising Zenodo for sharing the project's openly available data, GUESTXR can apply different levels of accessibility for this data taking into account any relevant issues (such as ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related, etc.).

More specifically, Zenodo offers the following levels of data accessibility:

- Open access: Data remains available for re-use. Nevertheless, the level in which this data can be re-used is determined also by their accompanied licence for re-use (see subsection 2.4.1).
- Embargoed status: Access to the data will be restricted until the end of the embargo period, at which time; the content will automatically become publicly available.
- Restricted access: The data will not be made publicly available and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of the project partner that has the responsibility of the data.
- Closed access: The data is protected against unauthorized access at all levels and only members of the consortium have the right to access it.

Project partners will mainly use the open access level to disseminate the project's data amongst the interested stakeholders. Nevertheless, in some cases embargo periods or

¹⁴ In order to discover a wide range of available research repositories please follow the link: <https://www.re3data.org/>

restricted access may be used. Data that will not be available for re-use will be accessible only by authorised partners of GUESTXR's consortium and /or authorised personnel from the REA of the Commission.

Moreover, GUESTXR will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications that may be produced in the framework of the project. In particular, according to the Grant Agreement, GUESTXR will:

- As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications as well as deposit, at the same time, the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication.
- Safeguard open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata shall be in a standard format and include the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”; the name of the action, acronym and grant number; the publication date, and length of the embargo period if applicable; and a PID.

Along these lines, this section has provided the methodology applied in the framework of GUESTXR so as to ensure that its data is as openly accessible as possible by any stakeholder that may find it interesting for re-use. In this context, GUESTXR also focuses on providing metadata standards and appropriate metadata vocabularies to increase its data interoperability. The following section provides further details in this respect.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and use data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data¹⁵. With that in mind, GUESTXR has adopted in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards and methods that will increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities.

More specifically, the interoperability of the data that will not be publicly shared will be facilitated by the use of the Dublin Core Metadata standard. This standard is a small “metadata element set” which accounts for issues that must be resolved in order to ensure that data meet traditional standards for quality and consistency, while still remaining broadly interoperable with other data sources in the linked data environment. The fifteen elements of the standard provide a vocabulary of concepts with natural-language definitions (e.g. title, creator, author, etc.) that are instantly converted into open machine-readable formats (such as XML, HTML, etc.), enabling machine-processability. Each element is optional and may be repeated, while the standard itself offer ways exist for refining them, encouraging the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes. The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard is presented by the following table¹⁶

¹⁵ L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives

¹⁶ Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

Table 7: Dublin Core Metadata Standard Vocabulary

No	Element	Element Definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.

Along similar lines, the interoperability of openly available data will be facilitated through Zenodo, since its metadata will be stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema. This encloses HTML microdata that allow machine-readable data to be embedded in HTML documents in the form of nested groups of name-value pairs. Moreover, the JSON schema provides a collection of shared vocabularies in microdata format that can be used to mark-up pages in ways that can be understood by the major search engines. Moreover, all metadata linked to the open data is exported via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested. The OAI-PMH develops and promotes interoperability standards that facilitate the efficient dissemination of data amongst diverse communities¹⁷.

2.4 Increase data reuse (through clarifying licenses)

2.4.1 License schemes to permit the widest use possible

The application of a licence to GUESTXR's open data is a simple way to ensure that any interested third-party can re-use it. In this context, licences are the instrument which permit a third-party to copy, distribute, display and/or modify the project's data only for the purposes that are set by the licence. Licences typically grant permissions on condition that certain terms are met. While the precise details vary, three conditions are commonly found in licences which are the attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality.

¹⁷ Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship.

Along these lines, GUESTXR publishes its openly available data under the Creative Commons licencing scheme to foster their re-use and build an equitable and accessible environment for them. In fact, Zenodo provides GUESTXR the opportunity to publish its open data under five Creative Common licences as follows:

Figure 2: CC BY-SA 4.0

- Creative commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, must be distributed under the same license as the original. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 3: CC BY 4.0

- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 4: CC BY-NC 4.0

- Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-ND 4.0) during which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0) based on which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get a permission by project partners first. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 5: CC BY-NC-ND 4.0

- Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) according to which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission by project partners first. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

With that in mind, the GUESTXR consortium considers that the CC BY-NC 4.0 is an appropriate licensing scheme to ensure the widest re-use of the data, while also taking into account the importance of recognising both the source and the authority of the data as well as safeguarding the interests of the GUESTXR project and its partners.

Nevertheless, different licensing schemes may be selected to better fit the need of GUESTXR's open data ensuring not only their long-term preservation and re-use but also the interests of the consortium along with the rights of individuals for whom the data is about. In such a case, this subsection of the DMP will be updated accordingly.

2.4.2 Availability for re-use

The re-use of data is a key component of GUESTXR's methodology for making data FAIR. In fact, making data available for re-use ensures interested stakeholders, other than project partners, can benefit from this data, contributing towards maximising the impact of the project. Rich metadata created based on metadata standards that enable proper discovery as well as appropriate licensing schemes facilitate the re-use of GUESTXR's open data, allowing them to find valuable utility.

In principle, it is expected that data will become available for re-use no later than 180 days after the end of its processing in the framework of the project (i.e. collection, anonymization, aggregation, etc.) to ensure that any additional data management activities required to this end do not compete with the timely delivery of the project's planned outputs. However, a partner seeking to publish scientific results or apply for patents may request to postpone the public release of the data for up to two years.

The period for which the data will remain available for re-use depends on the lifetime of their repository. In the case of data deposited to Zenodo, this is the lifetime of CERN's relevant laboratory, which at the moment has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years. In case Zenodo discontinues the data, this will be transferred and hosted to other suitable repositories.

3 Allocation of resources

3.1 Anticipated costs for making data FAIR

The costs required for making the data collected/generated during the course of GUESTXR's activities FAIR are integrated within the budget of the project. These anticipated costs will be needed to cover a set of specific data processing and data management activities. The data processing and data management activities are the following:

1. Collection
2. Documentation
3. Storage
4. Access And Security
5. Preservation
6. Availability and Reuse
7. Overall Data Management

A description about each data processing or data management activity is given below. The "Collection", "Documentation", "Storage, access and security", "Preservation" and "Availability and reuse" activities are part of the WP under which the respective data are processed so the required effort will be part of the respective WP. The overall data management plan activity is part of WP9.

The collection activity includes all activities necessary for acquiring external datasets (if required), gathering/generating new data, transcribing (if applicable), formatting and organising this data as well as acquiring informed consent from data subjects. This data processing activity reflects the majority of the costs required for making data FAIR as the majority of GUESTXR's data constitutes new data collected/generated over the course of the project. At the same time, data documentation costs address the effort required for describing data (e.g. marking data with variable and value labels, code descriptions, etc.) as well as creating well-defined metadata along with a meaningful description of the context and methodology of how data was collected/generated and processed (where necessary).

Costs for data storage include both the resources required for ensuring adequate storage space for the data as well as the effort necessary for conducting data back-ups, while data access and security costs encompass costs related to ensuring access to the data as well as for protecting it from unauthorised access or use or from disclosure. Given that the storage of GUESTXR's data will not require the procurement of additional space (other than what is already available to project partners) as well as that no special measures or software are required to access and secure the data (other than the what is inherently built in to the repositories of GUESTXR's data), such costs are kept to a minimum.

Data preservation costs, on the other hand, are estimated relatively higher than data storage, access and security costs, as additional effort may be required in several cases in order to convert the collected/generated data from their original form (e.g. physical interview transcripts) to an open and/or machine readable format suitable for long-term preservation (e.g. to an .xlsx format.). Adequate effort for data availability and re-use costs is also foreseen to safeguard the appropriate digitisation and anonymization of the data as well as cover any resources required for data sharing and cleaning. Along the same lines, appropriate effort is foreseen for overall data management as well, in order

to cover the effort related with the operationalisation of data management in the framework of GUESTXR.

Another anticipated cost can also be the fees that some publishers of scientific journals request to provide open access to articles or journals. Cost vary between different journals and publishers but for instance the fee to publish a hybrid journal of IEEE can be 1750\$.¹⁸ Finally, costs for long-term preservation in the framework of GUESTXR are assumed to be ineligible, since the open data of the project will be hosted in the repository of Zenodo free of charge.

3.2 Data management responsibilities

For the effective, proper and secure handling of the data collected/generated in the framework of GUESTXR, specific data management roles have been established within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP and are as follows.

Data Manager (DM): The DM is responsible of the overall data management in the framework of GuestXR project, including the elaboration of the DMP and its update (when necessary and with support of all partners). Additionally, the DM is responsible of establishing and monitoring the procedures for the collection and usage of data within the project lifetime supported by all WP and Task Leaders and assisted by the Scientific Leader. The DM will determine together with the generating/collecting partners the data that will be shared and will become publicly available in the appropriate platforms. The DM will support the generating/collecting partner to ensure the quality of the shared data providing some guidelines.

The DM is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the informed consent form and information sheet that can be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project. Finally, the DM will coordinate with SL, Work Package and Task Leaders to determine when and where shared data become available.

Work Package Leaders (WPL): The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. Moreover, they align with the PC and the respective Work Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. This includes the definition of access procedures as well as potential embargo periods along with any necessary software and/or other tools which may be required for data sharing and re-use. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

Work Task Leaders (WTL): The WTL act as data controllers of the data collected/generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership, determining the purposes and means of processing this data as well as safeguarding its appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data collected/ generated through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the

¹⁸ <https://open.ieee.org/index.php/about-ieee-open-access/faqs/>

use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymization techniques, creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

Data processors: Data processors are project partners that are tasked to collect, digitise, anonymise, store, destroy and/or otherwise process data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected/ generated within the framework of the project. They are responsible for appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data as well as for ensuring that the informed consent form and information sheet used to this end are properly adjusted to the needs of the activity they are participating and any particularities applicable to their organisation. Moreover, they are also responsible for managing the consents they have retrieved with a view to demonstrating their compliance with the relevant applicable EU and national regulation.

Data repositories: Data repositories are tasked with the storage and long-term preservation of the project’s data. In this respect, task repositories, such as Zenodo maintain and preserve the openly available data of GUESTXR, enabling its sharing and re-use. To this end, data repositories (e.g. Zenodo) may assign metadata and DOIs to the data, while also taking all the necessary measures to securely back-up the data and be in a position to restore it, safeguarding its long-term preservation. Accordingly, the GUESTXR internal site (SharePoint) shall securely store and preserve the project’s data available for sharing amongst authorised consortium members in the framework of the project.

In this context, the following table illustrates the allocation of data management responsibilities amongst the members of the GUESTXR consortium per data collected/generated under each WP.

Table 8: Data Management Responsibilities of GUESTXR partners under each WP

WP	WPL	Tasks	WTL Data Controllers	Data Processors
WP1	IDCH	T1.1	IDCH	UW
		T1.2	IDCH	UW
		T1.3	IDCH	UW, EUT
		T1.4	UM	IDCH
WP2	UM	T2.1	UW	-
		T2.2	UW	IDCH
		T2.3	UM	-
		T2.4	UM	-
		T2.5	GTEC	UM
WP3	VBW	T3.1	VBW	EUT, UB, IDCH
		T3.2	VBW	EUT, INRIA, IDCH
		T3.3	VBW	EUT
		T3.4	VBW	UB, INRIA
		T3.5	VBW	UB, INRIA
		T3.6	UB	-
WP4	INRIA	T4.1	IDCH	INRIA, UM, EUT

WP	WPL	Tasks	WTL Data Controllers	Data Processors
		T4.2	INRIA	-
		T4.3	EUT	INRIA, UM
		T4.4	VBW	INRIA
		T5.5	UM	INRIA, VBW, EUT, UM
WP5	VBW	T5.1	VBW	UM
		T5.2	IDCH	EUT, INRIA, UM
		T5.3	UB	VBW, INRIA, UM
		T5.4	UW	INRIA, UM
		T5.5	VBW	UM
		T5.6	UM	VBW, UB, EUT, INRIA, IDCH, UW
WP6	EUT	T6.1	EUT	VBW, UM, INRIA, UW, GTEC, UB
		T6.2	VBW	ALL
		T6.3	EUT	-
		T6.4	UB	-
		T6.5	UB	UM, UW, INRIA, EUT
WP7	EUT	T7.1	EUT	-
		T7.2	UB	-
		T7.3	EUT	

4 Data security

GUESTXR will securely handle any collected/generated data throughout its entire lifecycle as it is essential to safeguard this data against accidental loss and/or unauthorised manipulation. Particularly, in case of personal data collection/generation it is crucial that this data can only be accessible by those authorised to do so. With that in mind, the project's back-up and data recovery strategy aims at ensuring that no data loss will occur during the course and after the completion of GUESTXR, either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibit any unauthorised access.

In particular, all project partners responsible for processing data¹⁹ within their private servers will ensure that this data is protected, and any necessary data security controls have been implemented, so as to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and/or re-used within the framework of the project. In this case and to avoid data losses, the data will be backed up on a daily basis and the backed-up files will be stored in external hard disk drives so as to safeguard their preservation, while also enabling their recovery at any time. Moreover, integrity checks will be carried out once a month (or more often,

¹⁹ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

if deemed necessary) ensuring that the stored data has not been changed or corrupted. A tool that can support partners in undertaking integrity checks²⁰ is the MD5summer²¹ which can generate and verified MD5 checksums²².

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case there is a personal data breach, project partners will notify, without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, their competent national supervisory authorities (e.g. data protection authorities) as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach. Moreover, they will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

With that in mind, identification and authentication access controls play an important role in the context of the project, as they help partners to protect the data collected/generated during the course of GUESTXR and especially personal data. To this end, each project partner is responsible for and committed to ensuring the application of appropriate access controls to the data they are processing within their private servers of their organisation. At the same time, technical access controls are built into the GUESTXR internal site, setting out clear roles with access rights to the data stored there, so that only authorised personnel have access. Each project partner has unique accounts with one or more roles assigned to them enforcing role-based security when its staff processes the project's data. These accounts are username/password protected maximising access control.

On another note, GUESTXR's openly available data will be stored safely for long-term preservation on open repositories. Zenodo, an open repository, preserves data in the same cloud infrastructure as research data from CERN's Large Hadron Collider, using CERN's battle-tested repository software INVENIO, which is used by some of the world's largest repositories (such as INSPIRE HEP and the CERN Document Server). Along these lines, data is stored and backed-up in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple online replicas and independent replicas ensuring their long-term preservation as well as their recovery when necessary. Moreover, for each file two independent MD5 checksums are stored. One checksum is stored by INVENIO, used to detect changes to files made from outside of it whereas the other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks. In this context, access control is applied by the different level of openness that Zenodo allows (i.e. open, embargoed, restricted and closed).

²⁰ An integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state in order to detect any changes.

²¹ <http://www.md5summer.org/>

²² A checksum is small-sized data derived from a block of digital data for the purpose of detecting errors which may have been introduced during its transmission or storage. It is usually applied to an installation file after it is received from the download server. By themselves, checksums are often used to verify data integrity but are not relied upon to verify data authenticity.

5 Ethical aspects

GUESTXR entails activities which may involve the processing of data that does fall into a special category of personal data²³ (i.e. non-sensitive data). The collection/generation of this data from individuals participating in the project's activities is based upon a process of informed consent. In fact, any personal data collected/generated in the framework of GUESTXR is processed according to the principles laid out by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data which entered into force in May 2018 aiming to protect individuals' rights and freedoms in relation to the processing of their personal data, while also facilitating the free flow of such data within the European Union. Along these lines, data is collected/generated only for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes relative to project's objectives. Moreover, all project partners tasked with processing data during the course of GUESTXR fully abide with their respective applicable national as well as EU regulations.

In this respect, it is important to highlight that each project partner is responsible for ensuring that the templates for the Information Sheet as well as the Informed Consent Form are appropriately adjusted according to (i) the needs of the activity for which they are being used by them as well as to (ii) the relevant regulations applicable to their respective countries and/or organisation. Moreover, all partners should keep records to demonstrate that an individual has consented to processing of his / her personal data and use consent management mechanisms that make it easy for individuals to withdraw their consent.

Finally, no other national/funder/sectoral/departmental procedures for data management are currently used in the framework of GUESTXR.

GUESTXR project will work in the responsible research and innovation aspects in the framework of WP7 and the outcome of this work will be reported in dedicated deliverables. In particular more details with regards to ethics that may be applicable also in the case of data management will be reported in the deliverable D7.6. Responsible Research and Innovation.

5.1 Management of personal data

5.1.1 Basic concepts

What is personal data?

- According to Article 3 (1) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725: "personal data' means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more

²³ Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;"

Examples: name, address, identification number, pseudonym, occupation, e-mail, CV, location data, Internet Protocol (IP) address, cookie ID, phone number, data provided by smart meters, data held by a hospital or doctor.

- Individuals are not considered 'identifiable' if identifying them requires excessive effort.
- Completely anonymised data does not fall under the data privacy rules (as from the moment it has been completely anonymised).

Processing of personal data:

- According to Article 3 (3) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, processing of personal data refers to "any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction."

Stakeholders:

Controller:

- 'Controller' means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law;

Processor:

- 'processor' means a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller;

5.1.2 Personal data processed during the implementation of the project:

Below a table with information about the personal data that will be processed during the project execution is shown. The Data Protection Officer has already been informed about the personal data that will be processed in each organization and the measures that will be taken to protect data subjects: 1) Informed consent form and 2) Anonymization when possible or pseudo anonymization when the first is not feasible.

Table 9: 5.1.2 Personal data processed during the implementation of the project

EUT	Names, surnames, phone n ^o , e-mail, organisation, voice and image of the participants who will give explicit consent.
VBW	No personal data will be collected.
IDCH	Movements, decisions and speech. Behavioral information. Neuroscientific, physiological.
UM	Demographic data including age, gender and nationality. Behavioural data such as performance and reaction times as well as neuroscientific data.
INRIA	Identification data (name, first name, age, gender); subjective questionnaires (presence, personality, virtual embodiment, user experience..); Motions and actions (positions, speed...); performances related to tasks (errors, completion time...); physiological data (heart rate, breathing, body temperature, EEG); activity recording (video and audio).
UW	Demographic data including age, gender and nationality. Behavioural data such as performance and reaction times as well as neuroscientific data.
GTEC	No personal data will be collected.
UB	Identification data will be processed.

***NOTE that this information has been extracted from the Data Protection Officer Questionnaire from each partner (see annex IV).*

5.1.3 Technical and organisational measures that will be implemented to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants.

See annex IV with the Data Protection Officer Questionnaire from each partner.

5.1.4 Appointment of the Data Protection Officer (DPO).

Each of the institutions that will process personal data is required to detail the data protection policy that will follow in order to ensure the correct management of the personal data. Furthermore, they are required to count on a Data Protection Officer. See annex IV with the Questionnaire on Data Protection that partners are required to complete.

Below you will find a summary of the details on data protection officers appointed. You will find more information about the Data Protection regulations in annex IV which includes the Data Protection Officer questionnaire from each partner.

Table 10: Contact details of the DATA PROTECTION OFFICER'S

Contact details of the DATA PROTECTION OFFICER's	
EUT	Name: M ^a Carmen Calvo Tel: 0034 93 741 91 00 Email: dpo@eurecat.org
VBW	Name: Bernhard Spanlang Tel: +34 669355409 Email: privacy@virtualbodyworks.com
IDCH	Name: Ray Mike Tel: 09-9602400 Email: mike.ray@runi.ac.il
UM	Name: Vojtech Smekal Tel: +31 645705866 Email: y.smekal@maastrichtuniversity.nl
INRIA	Name: Anne Combe Tel: + 33 4 92 38 71 73 / +33 6 31 57 03 50 Email: dpo@inria.fr
UW	Name: Dominik Ferenc Tel: +48 22 55 20 000 Email: iod@adm.uw.edu
GTEC	Name: Christoph Schauer Tel: +43 7251 222 40 50 Email: schauer@gtec.at
UB	Name: Mr. Ruben Ortiz Address: Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes, 585, 08007 Barcelona Email: protecciodedades@ub.edu

5.1.5 How the 'data minimisation' principle will be ensured.

This project will ensure that the personal data that will be processed is:

- **adequate** – sufficient to properly fulfil the stated purpose;
- **relevant** – has a rational link to the purpose of the project; and
- **limited to what is necessary** – the partners in charge of the collection or processing of the data won't hold more needed for the project purpose.

To ensure this, each of the partners in charge of collecting data, should:

1. Identify the minimum amount of personal data needed to fulfil the project purpose.
2. Make sure that just this much information is collected/processed, but no more.
3. Be able to demonstrate that the methodology used counts with the appropriate processes to ensure that only the personal data is needed will be collected and held.

4. Ensure the right of rectification of the data providers: individuals have the right to complete any incomplete data which is inadequate for your purpose, under the right to rectification.
5. Periodically review the personal data held and delete any data that is not necessary anymore.

5.1.6 Description of the anonymization / pseudonymisation techniques that will be implemented.

In the framework of the research, the 'data minimisation' principle will be applied.

Whenever it is possible, the personal data will be substituted by anonymized or pseudonymised data and just in the cases when the research requires the actual personal data, this will be collected.

Even in the case when personal data is necessary, the research methodology will consider ways to make the data not easily linked to the participant (e.g. age range instead of actual age, group of birth countries instead of birth country).

What is anonymisation?

"Anonymisation" of data means processing it with the aim of irreversibly preventing the identification of the individual to whom it relates. Data can be considered effectively and sufficiently anonymised if it does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or where it has been rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.

In the case of anonymisation, by 'identification' we mean the possibility of retrieving a person's name and/or address, but also the potential identifiability by singling out, linkability and inference.

What is pseudonymisation?

"Pseudonymisation" of data means replacing any identifying characteristics of data with a pseudonym, or, in other words, a value which does not allow the data subject to be directly identified.

The GDPR and the Data Protection Act 2018 define pseudonymisation as the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that (a) such additional information is kept separately, and (b) it is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable individual.

Techniques:

There are, broadly speaking, two different families of anonymisation techniques: "randomisation" and "generalisation". Other techniques, such as "masking" or "pseudonymisation", which are aimed solely at removing certain identifiers, may also play a role in reducing the risk of identification.

Randomisation techniques involve the alteration of the data, in order to cut the link between the individual and the data, without losing the value in the data.

Given the personal data required established in the research methodology, once this is specified, each institution will confirm what are the techniques they will be able to put in place.

Example of anonymization techniques that will be used:

- Randomisation: Each participant will be identified with a randomly generated code that will substitute their name and surname or a code following an established syntax used for all use cases.
- Generalization: Aggregation/K-Anonymity: where personal identifiers are generalized into a range or group, for instance: Age: 30 → Age: 20-35

5.1.7 Informed consent procedures in regard to data processing

An informed consent emphasizes a process where the research participant must receive and comprehend information appropriately to make an autonomous decision.

An informed consent process can be termed as complete, valid, and meaningful if the following criteria are effectively satisfied: information disclosure, comprehension and voluntariness.

1. Information disclosure:

Previous of deciding if a member of staff wants to participate as a volunteer in the project study, the representatives of the project will provide them with an information sheet with information on the following topics:

- a. General overview of the project and its members
- b. The objective of the study
- c. Participant's rights
- d. How the personal data will be processed
- e. How will the participant benefit from this study

2. Comprehension:

After reading the information sheet, the participants will be requested to raise any questions and resolve any doubts they may have about their participation in the study. The informant will ensure that the participant understands the risks, benefits and significance of participating in this research.

3. Voluntariness:

Each institution will make sure that the volunteer's recruiting process is made in a way that ensures voluntariness. In the organisational context, voluntariness can be compromised by a variety of factors including feeling pressured by their own supervisors or other members of the organisation. In this regard, each institution will be asked to describe the procedure that has been put in place according to their usual procedures.

Once the person has been informed and has had the opportunity to ask all the questions and has voluntarily decided to participate, will be asked to complete and sign a consent form giving their consent to transfer their data and participate to the study. This consent

will confirm that the participants have followed the above mentioned process to enrol this study.

6 Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable version of the DMP describes the methodology that is planned to be employed in the framework of the GUESTXR project. The described methodology aims to safeguard the sound management of the data collected and generated during the course of the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them FAIR. Moreover, the DMP identifies the anticipated activities required for making data FAIR, outlines the provisions pertaining to their security as well as addresses the ethical aspects revolving around their collection/generation.

The DMP is considered to be a living document in the framework of GUESTXR and will be updated throughout the course of the project taking into account its latest developments and available results. In fact, the DMP will be reviewed and revalidated before each periodic project management report, and any updates will be included in the periodic project management reports. Ad hoc updates, may also be realised when deemed necessary, with a view to delivering an accurate, up-to-date and comprehensive DMP before the completion of the project. These updates will also be appended on the periodic project management reports.

Annex I – Privacy Policy of GUESTXR’s Web Portal

Who is the Data Controller of your personal data?

Data Controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“*Eurecat*” or “*Data Controller*”)

Tax Identification Code: G-66210345

Address: Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona (Spain)

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data Protections Officer’s email address: dpo@eurecat.org

What are the purposes and the legal basis for the processing of your personal data?

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as the data included at your query, given through the contact form, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact. The legal basis for its data processing is to develop the proper actions to answer the user’s contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...) as the data included at your query, given through the “User Group” contact form, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact as well as to inform or access at the GuestXR Group. The legal basis for its data processing is to develop the proper actions to answer the user’s contact (art 6.1 b) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...), for the purpose of give access to your data access to the GuestXR consortium partners, you may consult the detailed lit at [Consortium](#), in those cases that should be strictly necessary to manage properly the web form purposes. The legal basis for its data processing is the legitimate interest as well as the proper actions to execute the data purposes (art 6.1 b) and f) GDPR). You may obtain further information regarding the recipients of your data consulting “*Who are the recipients of your data?*” section at this Privacy Policy.

The Data Controller shall process your identifying and contact data (name, surname, email address...), for the purpose of subscribe and send GuestXR project information, as well as Eurecat’s general information, (both newsletters or solely the selected by the user). The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process data related your preferences (postal code, interests, preferences, professional information) given though the web forms, for the purpose profiling the user to sending the Newsletter segmented with contents that are aligned with the user interests. The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

The Data Controller shall process and have access to user’s navigation data (IP, location, browser...) because of the accessories cookies installed and agreed, for the purpose of improve the Web services and contents, further information regarding cookies data processing’s, consulting the [Cookies Policy](#). The legal basis for its data processing is the consent granted by the user (art 6.1 a) GDPR).

Who are the recipients of your data?

Eurecat is the main recipient of your data, however, they may be accessible to third parties that develop services to the Data Controller. When access to the user’s data is

required for the services developed, it shall be submitted and fulfill with the legal obligations, which are those of article 28 GDPR'S. In any event, the services providers shall not process the user's data for their own or different purposes and shall not overreach from the services purposes, and, in any case, shall not rent, sold, or make it available to third parties.

The Data Controller shall not transfer your data to third parties without your prior consent, which should fulfill the legal requirements.

The Data Controller may transfer your data to third parties in case of legal obligations to do so, without the user consent.

The personal data obtained by the web forms may be revealed to certain consortium partners whit whom Eurecat cooperate, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact, as well as to execute the proper actions to carry out the web form purposes for which the data was given. This data access by the consortium partners, does not entail a data assignment for its own purposes. You may consult the detailed list of the project consortium partner [here](#).

How long will your data be kept?

Eurecat shall process your data as long as is necessary to the purposes of the processing which the data were disclosed for and, in any case, until you ask its deletion.

Even if the User ask the deletion of the data, the Data Controller shall keep them blocked for the term required to afford legal obligations or make them available to third parties with the proper capacities because of legal issues.

Is your data subject to international data transfers?

Your data shall not be subjected to international data transfer, it means outside the European Economic Area ("EEA"). However, Eurecat may have services suppliers located or whom develop its services out of the EEA, in these sense, the Data Controller shall ensure to the User that their data object to international transfers shall be protected with the legal measures, that may consist on standard contractual clauses or privacy certifications, bot legal measures approved by the European Union.

Is your data subjected to profiling or automated decisions?

Your data shall not be subjected to automated decisions because of Eurecat's data processing's.

The Data Controller shall process your data for profiling purposes in case of you have consent the newsletter subscription where you have completed the optional web form parts related to your interests. Its profiling shall be done with the solely purpose of segment each newsletter to those subject matters that according to your profile may interest you and to avoid you the reception of all the newsletter activity. The profiling actions solely shall be done in case of you have given your consent to the Newsletter subscription, and the users profiling do not be used in other different ways or purposes.

Eurecat through the accessory cookies installed and agreed by the user, may process user's navigation data to profiling for the purposes of improve the Web services and contents, to obtain navigation and Web statistics, to develop and implement Web improvements. The cookies profiling is subjected to the cookies installed which are strictly linked to the user consent. You may consult further cookies information consulting the [Cookies Policy](#).

What are your personal data rights?

Current privacy laws granted several rights to the users regarding the processing of their data, main information about them is detailed herein:

1. **Right of access:** users are entitled to find out which of your personal data are processed and the processing purposes
2. **Right of rectification:** users are entitled to request the rectifications regarding their data at any time
3. **Right of erasure:** users are entitled to request, at any time, that their data shall be erased from the data controller storage. However, as set out in the above section related on data storage, in certain circumstances to compliance with the laws in force may prevent this right from being exercised
4. **Right to object:** users are entitled to object to their personal data from being processed in relation to any of each purposes processing's, pursuant to the privacy policies that may apply in each case.
5. **Right to restriction of processing:** users are entitled to request the restriction of purposes processing's in the following cases:
 1. If considers that their data are incorrect or inexact;
 2. If considers that their data has been processing with not the proper legal basis and considered to restrict the processing's instead of requests its erasures;
 3. If the data recorded are no longer required for the processing purposes which were collected for but need its storage to file a lawful claim;
 4. If the user having exercised its right to object for a specific purpose, is awaiting a reply from the data controller to this regard
6. **Right to data portability:** user is entitled to request that their personal data that were submitted to the data controller are being disclosed to another data controller, only in case that its request is technically possible and reasonable to do so.

How may you exercise your data rights?

Notwithstanding that your data has been collected within your consent or the proper legal basis, you may object to the data processing at any time whereby without consequences for you, however, depending on the right exercised certain services shall not be able to be rendered.

The users may exercise their rights according to the law terms and conditions by addressing to Eurecat through either of the following:

- (i). by email address to legal@eurecat.org
- (ii). by postal to Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avda. Universitat Autònoma 23, 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (BCN)

The user may have the right to contact to the Data Controller Data Protection Officer by email to dpo@eurecat.org

User, if considers that their data shall not been processed with legal basis or its requests or rights shall not been attended properly by the Data Controller, are entitled to file a claim upon the Supervisory Authority competent on data protection matters, it is the Agencia Española de Protección de Datos (www.aepd.es).

Annex II – Information Sheet and Informed Consent Form Templates

A. Information sheet (template)

1. Introduction

You have been invited to participate in the research and innovation project GuestXR (www.guestxr.eu), funded by the European Union within the framework of H2020 Research and Innovation programme (Ref. N° 101017884). Before you decide to participate and share your personal data with us, please take the time to carefully read this information sheet and ask any questions you may have.

2. What is GuestXR project all about?

This project aims to develop GuestXR, a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses eXtended Reality (virtual and augmented reality) as the medium to bring people together for immersive, synchronous face-to-face interaction with positive social outcomes. The critical innovation is the intervention of artificial agents that learn over time to help the virtual social gathering realise its aims.

GuestXR will be demonstrated in at least five different applications: 1) a conflict resolution application, 2) interactions involving participants with communication problems (i.e., auditory impairment); 3) contexts that trigger debate such as climate change; 4) & 5) another two applications that will be chosen from Open Calls to be launched along the project.

The GuestXR technology will be developed under the “Ethics by Design” approach.

3. Who are the consortium partners of GuestXR?

This project is conducted by the GuestXR consortium which consists of the following partner organisations: EURECAT FOUNDATION (Spain), VIRTUAL BODYWORKS SL (Spain), REICHMAN UNIVERSITY (Israel), UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT (Netherlands), INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE (France), UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI (Poland), G.TEC MEDICAL ENGINEERING GMBH (Austria), UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA (Spain).

4. What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to develop a safer environment for social interaction in extended reality (augmented and virtual reality) and to support participants achieve their goals when getting-together online. For this reason, we aim at collecting meaningful information that will help us to better shape project developments and to identify needs and expectations.

5. Is my participation in this study voluntary and what does it involve?

Your participation is entirely voluntary. If you consent to participate, we will ask you to sign an informed consent form and you will be given this information sheet to keep along with a copy of your signed informed consent form. Throughout the project (1st January 2022 – 31st December 2025), you may be invited to participate in activities such as technology user testing, surveys, individual interviews and collaborative discussions, relevant to the purpose of the GuestXR

project. These will all take place in one of the universities that are part of the consortium, and you will be informed in advance of the details and organisation of each activity. Your involvement in the project activities will only be for as long as you wish. You are free to decline to participate in any or all of these activities.

6. What if I change my mind later and I want to withdraw my consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time and ask us to have the personal data we collected from you erased and no longer use it. You do not have to give us any reason for making this choice and no adverse consequences will be implied for you if you decide to do so. Should you wish to withdraw your consent, please contact and convey your request to **<Insert name of contact person (DPO)>** (**<insert contact phone number>**, **<insert contact e-mail>**).

7. What type of personal data will be collected?

During your participation in this study, we will collect as little personal data as possible following the principle of “Data minimisation” principle. The personal data that will be collected will be the following: **<Insert type of personal data that will be collected>**.

8. How will you process my personal data?

Your personal data will be processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation of the EU as well as the respective applicable national regulation(s).

The data controller will collect your personal data through research tools **<Insert collection methods to be used (i.e. surveys, individual interviews, EEG, ECG, EMG or sensors)>**. This data will be securely stored by the consortium partners of GuestXR in charge of the collection and processing of the data and will be preserved in our records only for as long as necessary for us to comply with our contractual obligations to the funding authority of the project, namely the European Innovation Council (EIC) of the European Commission, and no longer than 5 years from the project’s completion. During this period your personal data will be accessible only by authorised individuals of GuestXR consortium partner and of the EIC. After this period your personal data will be deleted from the respective consortium partner’s records.

With your permission we would like to anonymise the personal data that you will provide us for this study, aggregate them with data collected from other participants of the study and analyse them with the aim of serving the purpose of this study. Moreover, we would like to archive and disseminate this anonymous aggregated data for non-commercial re-use through trusted open data repositories, such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), making it available for the benefit of current and future research projects. The anonymization and aggregation of the data will help ensure that you cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from this survey.

9. What are my rights on data protection in the context of my participation in this study?

Your participation in this survey encompasses a number of rights which you can exercise at any time. In particular, you have the:

- **Right to be informed:** You have the right to be informed about the collection and use of your personal data, including the purpose for which we are processing this data, the period that we will retain it and with whom we will share it.
- **Right of access:** You have the right to ask from us to confirm whether or not we are processing personal data concerning you. Where that is the case, you can access your personal data that we are processing (including copies of this data) and relevant supplementary information.
- **Right to rectification:** You have the right to request from us modifications to your personal data in case you believe that this data is not up to date, complete or accurate.

- **Right to erasure** (“right to be forgotten”): You have the right to ask us to erase your personal data that we are processing.
- **Right to restrict processing**: You have the right to request from us to restrict the processing of your personal data, with a view to limiting the way that we use this data.
- **Right to data portability**: You have the right to ask for your personal data to be provided back to you or transferred to a third party.
- **Right to object**: You have the right to object to us processing your personal data at any time for reasons related to your particular situation.
- **Right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing** (including profiling), which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.
- **Right to lodge a complaint**: In any case, you also have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent data protection authority.

10. Will I benefit from this study?

By participating in this study, you will be contributing to the resulting technology of the GuestXR project that intends to make immersive social interaction spaces safer for everyone, and more inclusive. This is an opportunity for you to help design this technology of the future, according to your needs and preferences. Furthermore, you may get the chance to participate in future project activities, should you wish to, getting early access to the GuestXR Project activities.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet!

B. Consent form (template)

Pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679, of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the relevant State regulations, **<Insert name of the institution collecting & processing the data>**, the controller, hereby provides the following information regarding data protection:

Controller: **<Name of the institution collecting & processing the data>**

ID: **<VAT number>**

Registered Office: **<Registered office address >**

Mail address: **<legal contact email address>**

Phone Number: **<phone number>**

Data protection officer: **<Data protection officer email address>**

Purpose: *Collecting and processing the necessary personal data for the GuestXR study. The controller of the data (see above) will anonymise the personal data that you will provide, aggregate them with data collected from other participants in this study and analyse them with the aim of serving the purpose of this study.*

Basis: *The basis for the processing is the consent granted by the data subject for this purpose.*

Recipients: As mentioned in the point 6 of the information sheet, your personal data will be securely stored by the consortium partners of GuestXR in charge of the collection and processing of the data.

The personal data will not be disclosed to third parties unless there is a legal obligation to do so, or express authorisation is granted.

Rights: *To access, rectify and delete the data and limit and oppose the processing thereof or exercise the right to portability of the data. These rights may be exercised, by submitting a request by email to **<Data protection officer email address>**.*

*In any case, you have the right to file a claim or obtain further information about any of these rights, you may contact the **Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6 in Madrid, Spain)**.*

Your consent may be revoked at any time.

Storage: *The personal data will be kept while the reason lasts for which they were provided, and their deletion or cancelation has not been requested.*

<Insert name of the institution collecting & processing the data> hereby informs you that it meets all the requirements stipulated by the data protection regulations and has in place all the technical and organisational measures to ensure the security of personal data. Moreover, in the event of any breach by the controller in the processing of your personal data, you are entitled to file a claim with the **Spanish Data Protection Agency**.

Principal Investigator: Mel Slater
Project Coordinator: Aurora Sesé
Project reference: 101017884
Participant Name and Surname:

(THIS FORM MUST BE COMPLETED PRIOR TO THE INTERVIEW/SURVEY)

1. I confirm that I have read the GuestXR Information Sheet, understand the Information Sheet provided to me for the study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason, without my legal rights being affected.
3. I understand that my personal data, which link me to research data, will be kept securely in accordance with data protection regulations (General Data Protection Regulation, and national regulation), and only shared to the immediate research team of the project consortium.
4. I understand that the research data, which will be anonymized (not linked to me), may be shared with others.
5. I understand that confidentiality will be maintained, and it will not be possible to identify me from any publications arising from the study.
6. I understand that some parts of the data collected for the study may be looked at by representatives of regulatory authorities to check that the study is being carried out correctly. All personnel have a duty of confidentiality to me as a research participant. I give permission for this.
7. I agree to take part in the above study.
8. I have voluntarily made the decision of taking part of this study.

Name of Participant Date Signature

Name of Person taking consent Date Signature

Annex III – Image rights Consent Form Template

PREAMBLE

As a member of the GuestXR consortium, you will be invited to participate to different online, virtual and face to face meetings and activities in the framework of the GuestXR project. During your attendance to these meetings and activities, there may be video recording and photo shooting. The resulting videos and pictures may be used to disseminate the GuestXR project and the work that your organisation is doing.

The GuestXR project (www.guestxr.eu), is a technology research and innovation project funded by the European Union in the framework of the H2020 program (reference number: 101017884).

This project aims to develop GuestXR, a socially interactive multisensory platform system that uses eXtended Reality (virtual and augmented reality) as the medium to bring people together for immersive, synchronous face-to-face interaction with positive social outcomes. The critical innovation is the intervention of artificial agents that learn over time to help the virtual social gathering realise its aims.

In some of the project meetings/activities, Fundació Eurecat may be in charge of the recording and shooting of the images and its edition.

DATA PROCESSING AND AUTHORISATION OF THE RIGHT TO ONE'S OWN IMAGE

Regarding the right to one's own image, referred to in Article 18.1 of the Spanish Constitution and governed by Organic Act 1 of 5 May 1982 on the Right to Honour, Personal and Family Privacy and One's Own Image, Fundació Eurecat requests that you grant your consent to be able to record, disseminate or publish, by any means, the photographs and videos in which you fully or partially appear as a real person or with your avatar, and in which you are clearly identifiable for informative, dissemination and advertising purposes of the activities and/or events in relation to the GuestXR project.

This image/video will not expressly affect your privacy and may only be used for the activities and/or events held by Fundació Eurecat.

<input type="checkbox"/>	YES , I authorise Fundació Eurecat to use my image (including photo and video of the real person or its avatar), free of charge and with no time or territorial limit, in accordance with the terms and conditions specified in this document.
<input type="checkbox"/>	NO , I do not authorise Fundació Eurecat to use my image (including photo and video of the real person or its avatar), free of charge and with no time or territorial limit, in accordance with the terms and conditions specified in this document.

Pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and the relevant State regulations, Fundació Eurecat, the controller, hereby provides the following information regarding data protection:

Data Controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT

ID: G66210345

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23 – 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès (Barcelona), Spain

Mail address: legal@eurecat.org

Phone number: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection officer: dpo@eurecat.org

Purpose: *In the framework of the European project GuestXR (www.guestxr.eu), of which your organisation is part, Fundació Eurecat may process identifying data (e.g. image, voice, avatar) for the purposes of recording the project meetings, managing your participation, as well as for dissemination and communication actions related to the GuestXR project within the communication project channels.*

Basis: The legal basis for the processing is the consent granted by the data subject for this purpose (GDPR article 6.1b).

Recipients: The main recipient of the data is Fundació Eurecat. The data could be accessible to the data controller suppliers in case that this is necessary to develop certain services arranged, this access shall fulfil to the legal requirements. The data may be ceded in case of legal obligations.

Storage: The personal data will be kept while the purposes last for which they were provided, and their deletion or cancelation has not been requested.

Automated decisions and profiling: the data processed shall not be object to automated decisions neither to profiling.

Rights: To access, rectify, revoke, and delete the data and limit and oppose the processing thereof or exercise the right to portability of the data. These rights may be exercised, according to the terms and conditions in the law in force, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or by submitting a request by email to legal@eurecat.org

You have the right to contact to Fundació Eurecat Data Protection Officer, submitting an email to dpo@eurecat.org

If they do not obtain a satisfactory reply and wish to file a claim or obtain further information about any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6 in Madrid, Spain).

Mr./Ms. [.....], holding National Identity Card Number or Passport Number [.....] I hereby state that understand these clauses and, by signing this document, I state that I accept the contents thereof and expressly consent to the personal data being processed as stated in the aforementioned terms.

In [.....], on [...] [.....] 2022

Signature

Annex IV – Data Protection Officer Questionnaires

Eurecat

Fundació Eurecat - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: M^a Carmen Calvo Tel: 937419100 Email: dpo@eurecat.org</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?) YES</p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project Eurecat will directly collect personal data In the frame of GuestXR project Eurecat will analyse and process collected data</i></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p><i>The data that Eurecat will process are: name, surnames, phone n^o, e-mail, organisation, voice and image of the participants who will give explicit consent. The purpose of the processing will be project dissemination and communication as well as to develop an avatar.</i></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p><i>DPO supported with the internal Legal department are involved watching over the process and making the necessary actions to fulfil with the national data protection law (which is Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights).</i></p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p><i>Fundació Eurecat has implemented technical and organisational measures with the commitment to protect the systems and the data kept. In addition, Dpo and the Legal Department are actively involved to align all the business activity to the GDPR requirements, in the accordance with the foregoing, the are several actions as well as, the redaction of policies and procedures which are ongoing.</i></p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p><i>Fundació Eurecat, as a Spanish entity, has assigned the Spanish national supervisory authority, which is Agencia Española de Protección de Datos. The national law, has not include the obligation to notify the type of the data processing due the GuestXr project.</i></p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
M^a Carmen Calvo

Role
<Data protection officer>

Signature

CALVO VALERA
MARIA DEL
CARMEN -
43435369F

Firmado digitalmente
por CALVO VALERA
MARIA DEL CARMEN -
43435369F
Fecha: 2022.03.10
08:20:47 +01'00'

Virtual Bodyworks - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation: Virtual Bodyworks SL	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Bernhard Spanlang Tel: +34 869355409 Email: privacy@virtualbodyworks.com</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>In the frame of GuestXR project Virtual Bodyworks will not directly collect any personal data.</p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p>Data processing and management is in compliance with Data Protection Regulation, and in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR), and Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 of 5 December, on Personal Data Protection and the Guarantee of Digital Rights (LOPDGDD)</p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p>Virtual Bodyworks has developed an internal DATA PROTECTION plan in the company on date March 10th, 2021. All measures will be taken into account in the course of the project.</p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p>The Spanish Data Protection Agency is the public authority in charge of ensuring compliance with the GPPR, the national data protection law in Spain.</p> <p>Virtual Bodyworks is governed by Spanish legislation and jurisdiction. For any dispute that could arise VIRTUAL BODYWORKS, S.L. submits to the courts and tribunals of Barcelona (Spain).</p> <p>In the project context there is no obligation to notify to the Spanish Data Protection Agency.</p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
Bernhard Spanlang

Role
Data protection officer

Signature

VIRTUAL BODYWORKS SL
 Sant Antoni Maria Claret, 167
 08025 Barcelona
 CIF B66044371

Brain, Cognition, and Technology Institute - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Ray Mike Tel: 099602400 Email: mike.ray@runi.ac.il</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>YES</p> <p>In the frame of GuestXR project BCT institute will directly collect, analyse and process some personal collected data</p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p>During the project we will conduct behavioural studies and neuroimaging studies in which data will be collected and recorded. However, the data will be anonymized, with names of participants being recorded as participant codes. Laboratory computers are password protected and personal only to the lab member/s involved in the study.</p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p>Yes, the following revisions and policies have been suggested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data will not be saved on the cloud or Dropbox • Only researchers working on specific studies will have access to the data
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p><i>We have information security policies and procedures:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Encryption of information files</i> 2) <i>Granting permissions only to employees associated with the specific study.</i> 3) <i>Requesting permissions for new employees in an orderly and documented manner (ie through the reading system), at the same time revoking permissions for employees who do not need access to research.</i> 4) <i>Using the QUALTRICS platform where access is secure.</i> 5) <i>Employees signing confidentiality forms.</i> 6) <i>Signing partners/contractors on confidentiality forms.</i> 7) <i>Retention of information throughout the declared length of the study.</i> 8) <i>The information collected should not be passed on to a third party.</i>

	9) <i>The questionnaire for experimenters must define their right to be forgotten, the duration of the information in which the information will be kept, and an address for the questions.</i>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p><i>The Privacy Protection Authority is the body that regulates, supervises, and enforces according to the Privacy Protection Law in Israel. As a regulator working to protect the basic right to privacy and the protection of personal information in Israel, the Privacy Protection Authority is responsible for protecting personal information in digital databases and for strengthening the right to privacy.</i></p> <p><i>The Privacy Protection (Information Security) Regulations that entered into force in May 2018 define the level of information security required of every factor in the Israeli economy, both public and private, who manage or process digital personal information about people and establish mechanisms designed to make information security part of the organization's management routine. The purpose of the regulations is to increase and strengthen the protection of the personal information of each and every one of us, through clear information security requirements that entities and organizations must comply with, depending on the sensitivity and scope of the personal information managed or held by them.</i></p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
Mike Ray

Role
Data protection officer

Signature

מייק ריי
סמנכ"ל אגף מערכות מידע וטכנולוגיות
אוניברסיטת רייכמן

15-05-2022

<Advanced Reality Lab> - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Ray Mike Tel: 09-9602400 Email: mike.ray@runi.ac.il</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>YES</p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project ARL will directly collect some personal data</i></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p><i>During the project we assume that we would like to conduct some empirical studies with the participation of students as subjects. The software systems will record all the activities of the participants: movement, decisions (presses on controllers) and speech. The files are saved in different files for each participant and each session: motion logs, action logs, sound files, text files extracted from the sound files - all on a timeline.</i></p> <p><i>Furthermore, all researchers receive instructions regarding the privacy of the data: Do not list the name of the participant in the study anywhere but only the participant code. Laboratory computers are protected by a password provided only to researchers conducting laboratory research.</i></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p><i>Yes, the officer has suggested revisions of our data policies as follows:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>We will not save research data on "cloud drives" such as Dropbox. The information must be stored either in the departmental network drive or in ONE DRIVE, which is an enterprise and is subject to an enterprise information security policy.</i> - <i>Additionally, only the researchers working on specific studies will have access to the data in those studies (based on encrypted folders per study).</i>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p><i>We have information security policies and procedures:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>Encryption of information files</i> 2) <i>Granting permissions only to employees associated with the specific study.</i> 3) <i>Requesting permissions for new employees in an orderly and documented manner (ie through the reading system), at the same time revoking permissions for employees who do not need access to research.</i>

	<p>4) Using the QUALTICS platform where access is secure.</p> <p>5) Employees signing confidentiality forms.</p> <p>6) Signing partners/contractors on confidentiality forms.</p> <p>7) Retention of information throughout the declared length of the study.</p> <p>8) The information collected should not be passed on to a third party.</p> <p>9) The questionnaire for experimenters must define their right to be forgotten, the duration of the information in which the information will be kept, and an address for the questions.</p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p>The Privacy Protection Authority is the body that regulates, supervises, and enforces according to the Privacy Protection Law in Israel. As a regulator working to protect the basic right to privacy and the protection of personal information in Israel, the Privacy Protection Authority is responsible for protecting personal information in digital databases and for strengthening the right to privacy.</p> <p>The Privacy Protection (Information Security) Regulations that entered into force in May 2018 define the level of information security required of every factor in the Israeli economy, both public and private, who manage or process digital personal information about people and establish mechanisms designed to make information security part of the organization's management routine. The purpose of the regulations is to increase and strengthen the protection of the personal information of each and every one of us, through clear information security requirements that entities and organizations must comply with, depending on the sensitivity and scope of the personal information managed or held by them.</p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
<xxx>
Michael Ray

Role
<Data protection officer>
מייק ריי
סמנכ"ל אגף מערכות מידע וטכנולוגיות
אוניברסיטת רייכמן

Signature
[Handwritten Signature]

B. Oh 2028

UM

Maastricht University - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Vojtěch Smekal Tel: +31 645705866 Email: v.smekal@maastrichtuniversity.nl</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>YES</p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project UM will directly collect any personal data.</i></p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project UM will analyse and process collected data.</i></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p><i>Personal data will be collected during the completion of neuroscientific and psychological studies, and this will include demographic data including age, gender, and nationality, behavioural data, such as performance and reaction times to various tasks, as well as neuroscientific data collected using various techniques, such as fMRI and EEG. Data will be anonymised where possible, so that it cannot be linked to the individual, and in all cases consent will be collected from each individual for the storing and processing of their data.</i></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p>N/A</p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p><i>Maastricht University has a Data Management Code of Conduct (which can be found here: https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/research/integrity-ethics/management-research-data), which will be strictly adhered to throughout this project.</i></p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p><i>The Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens is the supervising data protection authority in the Netherlands. In the Dutch GDPR Implementation Act 05/2018, it is made clear that adhering to the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679, the processing of personal data is for the purposes of scientific research, as long as adequate safeguards are provided. The law can be found here: https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0040940/2021-07-01</i></p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
Vojtěch Smekal

Role
Data protection officer

Signature

Inria - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.
	<p>YES</p> <p>Name: Anne COMBE Tel: + 33 4 92 38 71 73 / +33 6 31 57 03 50 Email: dpo@inria.fr</p>
2	If the answer to question 1 is yes
	Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)
	YES
	In the frame of GuestXR project Partner Inria will directly collect personal data.
	In the frame of GuestXR project Partner Inria will analyse and process collected data.
Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.	
The personal data which are expected to be collected in our experiments a priori enclose:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identification and characteristics of the participants (name, first name, age, gender) • subjective questionnaires (presence, personality, virtual embodiment, user experience, etc) • motions and actions (position, speed, etc) • performances related to a 2D or 3D interaction tasks (errors, completion time, etc) • physiological data (heart rate, breathing, body temperature, EEG) • activity recordings (video and/or audio) 	
Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?	
NA	
3	Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?
	The personal data protection governance of our organization is based on the General Policy for Information Security, the GDPR Privacy Policy and the annual GDPR Action Plan.
	The actors of this governance are: the DPO, the Ethics Committee, the Chief Information Security Officer, the Legal Department, the Information Systems Security Correspondent.
The main parts of the Data Protection Policy are: the compliance to GPDR analysis, the risk analysis, the records of processing activities, the advice of Ethics Committee.	
4	What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the

	data processing in the context of the project?
	The Data Protection Authority for our organization is the "Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés" (CNIL) in France. In the related law "Loi n° 78-17 du 6 janvier 1978 relative à l'informatique, aux fichiers et aux libertés", and all the data processing of our organization must be notified to our DPO.

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name	Role	Signature
Anne COMBE	Data Protection Officer	

University of Warsaw - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Dominik Ferenc Tel: +48 22 55 20 000 Email: iod@adm.uw.edu.pl</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>YES</p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project the University of Warsaw will directly collect personal data.</i></p> <p><i>In the frame of GuestXR project the University of Warsaw will analyse and process collected data.</i></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p><i>Personal data will be collected during the completion of neuroscientific and psychological studies, and this will include demographic data including age, gender, and nationality, behavioural data, such as performance and reaction times to various tasks, questionnaire data, as well as neuroscientific data collected using various techniques, such as fMRI and EEG. Data will be anonymised where possible, so that it cannot be linked to the individual, and in all cases consent will be collected from each individual for the storing and processing of their data.</i></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p><i>Data processing and management is in compliance with the national data protection law</i></p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p><i>The University of Warsaw employs organizational measures that are in line with the EU legislation under the Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council (EU) 2016/679 of April 27, 2016, on the protection of individual persons with regard to the personal data processing and on the free flow of such data, and also repealing Directive 95/46/EC (general regulation on data protection) (Official Journal EU L 119 of 04.05.2016, page 1, with subsequent changes). If the University of Warsaw works with sensitive data, we will collect, store, secure, transmit, preserve, and when needed, destroy it in accordance with the University of Warsaw organizational measures.</i></p> <p><i>The University of Warsaw has instructions for the identification, reporting, and immediate treatment of incidents of breach of personal data security within the used processing system. All personnel at the University of Warsaw are trained in matters of personal data protection, as well as in special information-related functions of the information systems being used. Security</i></p>

	<i>management staff are regularly provided with ongoing specialized training on technological developments in the field of information security.</i>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p><i>Personal Data Protection Office is the major data supervising authority in Poland. In the related law Act of 10 May 2018 on the Protection of Personal Data it is mentioned that data can be collected and processed for purely research and scientific purposes, provided that anonymity is guaranteed and all necessary measures for the protection of the privacy of the involved physical persons have been taken. Link to related law: https://uodo.gov.pl/en/594</i></p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
Andrzej Nowak

Role
<Data protection officer>

Signature
Andrzej Nowak

GTEC

<GTEC> - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Christoph Schauer Tel: +43 7251 222 40 50 Email: schauer@gtec.at</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p><YES></p> <p><In the frame of GuestXR project GTEC "will not" directly collect any personal data></p> <p><In the frame of GuestXR project GTEC "will not" analyse and process collected data></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p><N/A></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p><N/A></p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p> <p>N/A</p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p><N/A></p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
<07th of April 2022>

Role
<Data protection officer>

Signature
Christoph Schauer

UB - Questionnaire on Data Protection

Data protection officer (DPO) at your legal entity / organisation:	
1	<p>Has a data protection officer/supervisor been appointed at your organization? If so, please provide the contact details.</p> <p>Name: Mr. Ruben Ortiz (Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes, 585, 08007 Barcelona)</p> <p>Email: protecciodedades@ub.edu</p>
2	<p>If the answer to question 1 is yes</p> <p>Has the data protection officer/supervisor already been informed about the data processing (planned to be) carried out in the course of the project? (If not will s/he be informed/involved when the collection of personal data starts?)</p> <p>DPO: I have received the grant agreement and the Annex I (Part A and Part B) of this research project. Therefore, I have received information regarding the project and the processing that the UB research team will carry out. As the research team has explained to me, they will send me detailed information regarding the personal data processing when they have designed processing and when they ask for ethical approval.</p> <p><i><In the frame of GuestXR project UB will analyse and process collected data></i></p> <p>Please explain what kind of personal data and how data will be handled.</p> <p>DPO: Data collected during this study will be pseudonymized. The experimenters will not have access to the identities of the respondents. The IP will be the only person with access to the list that correlates identifiers with pseudonyms.</p> <p>Results will only be given in aggregate. If in the write up of the studies we use something that the participant writes it will be anonymous.</p> <p>When the participant accepts to participate in our studies, they will have read the information provided about this study. From the Data Protection Office, we have worked with the research team to include in the information sheets the information required by Article 13 of GDPR in the framework of previous projects. Moreover, we will advise them on the compliance with personal data protection obligations in the framework of this research project.</p> <p><i><...></i></p> <p>Has s/he already expressed an opinion on the compliance with the national data protection law (Please provide any statements)?</p> <p>DPO: I will provide them with advising on compliance with personal data protection during the project.</p>
3	<p>Does your organization have data protection guidelines (e.g. on technical and organizational measures of data protection)? Will these apply to the data processed in the course of the project?</p>

<p>The Data protection office has provided the following list of security measures:</p> <p><u>Automated processing</u></p> <p><i>Identification and authentication: the necessary mechanisms must be established to guarantee the unequivocal and personalized identification and authentication of users. However, the periodicity of driving licenses is no more than three months and the licenses must have, at least, a numeric character, a capital letter and a special character.</i></p> <p><i>Access control; each user must have access to the information necessary for the development of their functions and mechanisms must be established to prevent access to resources that differ from those authorized. In addition, there must be an updated list of users and user profiles, and the authorized accesses for them.</i></p> <p><i>Limitation of unauthorized access attempts: there must be a mechanism to prevent repeated attempts at unauthorized access to an information system (for example, a maximum number of attempts to enter a password).</i></p> <p><i>Logging of access to information or documentation: when processing specially protected data, it is required to record user activity (what is done with the data). Thus, each time a user attempts to access personal data, the user's identification, the data and time of the access attempt, the name under which access is attempted, the type of access (query or modification) and whether access is denied or authorized by the access control system must be recorded. In those cases where access has been authorized, information must also be stored to identify what data was accessed. Access logging mechanisms cannot be deactivated, nor can the information they collect be manipulated. This information must be kept for two years and at least every month the person responsible for security (LOPD Security Commission) must review this information and submit a report to the person responsible for the file (General Secretariat).</i></p> <p><i>Physical access control: only persons authorized by the principal investigator may physically access the spaces where the physical equipment supporting the information systems is installed.</i></p> <p><i>Register of entry and arrangement of supports (article 97 RLOPD): there must be a register of entry and exit of supports and documents, which must allow to know the type of support or document that has entered or left, along with the data and time, who is the sender or recipient, the number of documents or supports, the type of information they contain, the processing mechanism and who has been the person responsible for the reception or delivery.</i></p> <p><i>Management of supports and documents: any type of classified information with personal data outside the premises, including processing by e-mail, must be authorized in writing by the principal investigator. Likewise, the transport of documents or supports must be done with measures that prevent sustenance, loss or unauthorized access. In addition, whenever a document or support is to be destroyed or erased, measures must be taken to prevent access to the information it contains or its subsequent recovery.</i></p> <p><i>Encryption of media during transport and protection of documentation: certain precautions must be taken during the transport of media with information or documentation. In the case of the distribution of media, companies must cancel the encrypted or use alternative mechanisms that prevent access or manipulation of the information during transport.</i></p> <p><i>Encryption of telecommunications: when high-level data is transmitted through public telecommunication networks or wireless electronic communication networks, the information must be encrypted or any other mechanism must be implemented to make the information unreadable and prevent manipulation.</i></p>

<p><i>Work outside the usual processing premises or locations: to store personal data on portable devices or to process them outside the premises and facilities of the University of Barcelona, prior written authorization from the principal investigator will be required.</i></p> <p><i>Encryption of portable devices: if the information is found on portable computers outside the usual processing premises, the information must also be encrypted. It is important to bear in mind that the processing of specially protected data in portable devices that cannot be encrypted must be avoided.</i></p> <p><i>Support and recovery copies: action procedures must be established to make security copies at least once a week and procedures for the recovery of the data to the state in which they were at the time of loss or destruction. The principal investigator must verify every six months that the copy and restoration procedures are working correctly.</i></p> <p><i>Avoid concurrence of risks in copies and recovery procedures: security copies and recovery procedures must be kept in a different location from where the computer equipment containing the data is kept so that they are not under the same physical threats. In this differentiated location, the same security measures must be complied with as in the initial location.</i></p> <p><i>Incident register: A procedure should be established for reporting and managing incidents (understood as any anomaly that affects or may affect data security), as well as creating a record of the type of incident, when produced or detected, the person who notified it, who has been notified, what actions have been taken and what corrective measures have been implemented so that the same incident does not happen again.</i></p> <p><i>Record the recovery procedures in the incident log: the incident log must also include information on the recovery procedures that have been necessary to carry out as a result of an incident. In these cases, it must be indicated who has carried out the data recovery process, which data have been restored and, if necessary, if data have been recovered manually.</i></p> <p><u>Non-automated processing (e.g. personal data on paper)</u></p> <p><i>Archiving criteria: the archiving of files or documents must be carried out guaranteeing the correct conservation of the documents, the location and consultation of the information and making it possible to exercise the rights of opposition to the processing, access, rectification and cancellation.</i></p> <p><i>Storage devices in locked areas: the cabinets, filing cabinets and devices in which the information is stored must be located in protected areas by means of access doors that are locked and that incorporate locking devices, such as locks or other mechanisms, that prevent free access to the rooms. If the premises do not permit the implementation of this measure, alternative measures must be adopted and must be justified.</i></p> <p><i>Access control: each user must have access only to the information necessary for the development of their functions and mechanisms must be established to prevent access to resources with rights different from those authorized. In addition, there must be an updated list of users and user profiles, and the authorized accesses for each of them.</i></p> <p><i>Make it difficult to access storage devices containing documents: access to filing cabinets, cupboards, drawers, etc. where documents are stored must be made by means of some mechanism that hinders opening (panes or similar). If, due to the characteristics of the document storage devices, it is not possible to implement mechanisms that hinder opening, measures must be taken to prevent access by unauthorized persons.</i></p> <p><i>Access to information or documentation: when there are documents that can be used by</i></p>

	<p><i>multiple users, mechanisms must be established to identify the accesses made to this documentation.</i></p> <p><i>Custody of the documents by the personnel: when the documentation is outside the places destined to its storage or archive, usually because it is being used, the person in charge of this documentation has to take care of it and has to prevent, at all times, unauthorized persons from having access to it.</i></p> <p><i>Control of the copy or reproduction of documents: any copy or reproduction of a paper document can only be made under the control of the principal investigator.</i></p> <p><i>Destruction of useless copies: when copies of documents are no longer useful they must be destroyed, in order to avoid access to the information they contain or that this information can be recovered (this implies the use of paper shredders or similar procedures).</i></p> <p><i>Management of supports and documents: any removal of information with personal data outside the premises, including transmission by e-mail, must be authorized in writing by the principal investigator. In addition, the transport of documents or supplies must be carried out with measures to prevent their removal, loss or unauthorized access. In addition, whenever a document or support is to be destroyed or deleted, measures must be taken to prevent access to the information it contains or its subsequent recovery.</i></p> <p><i>Transfer of documentation: whenever the physical transfer of documentation is carried out, measures must be taken to prevent access to the information being transferred or its manipulation.</i></p> <p><i>Work outside the usual premises or locations of processing: in order to store personal data in portable devices or to process them outside the premises and facilities of the University of Barcelona, prior written authorization from the principal investigator will be required.</i></p> <p><i>Incident register: the principal investigator must establish a procedure for notifying and managing incidents, in addition to creating a record of the type of incident, when it occurred or was detected, the person who notified the incident, who was notified, what actions were taken and what corrective measures were implemented to ensure that the same incident does not happen again.</i></p>
4	<p>What is the competent supervisory authority (i.e. data protection authority) for your organization? Is there an obligation under national law to notify this authority about the data processing in the context of the project?</p> <p>According to the Article 156 of the Organic Law 6/2006, dated 19 July, reforming the Statute of Autonomy of Catalonia, and the Article 3 of the Law 32/2010, of 1 October, on the Catalan Data Protection Authority, the competent supervisory authority of the processings of the University of Barcelona is the Catalan Data Protection Authority.</p> <p>Considering the Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights, there is not an obligation to notify this authority about any data processing in the context of the project.</p>

I confirm the correctness of the above.

Name
Ruben Ortiz Uroz

Role
Data protection officer

Signature

RUBEN ORTIZ 2022.05.1
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